

THE INFLUENCE OF EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT AND ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE WITH JOB SATISFACTION AS AN INTERVENING VARIABLE

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Abstract : The power generation industry is a crucial sector in supporting the government's program to provide electricity for all Indonesian citizens. To accelerate the achievement of the vision and mission of the power generation industry, optimal support from human resources is needed. This study aims to determine whether employee engagement and organizational justice affect employee performance with job satisfaction as an intervening variable at PT. Berkat Bima Sentana. The research was conducted on 129 employees at PT. Berkat Bima Sentana using proportionate random sampling technique and Slovin's formula with a margin of error of 5%, resulting in 98 respondents. The data collection techniques used were primary data in the form of questionnaires and secondary data obtained through documentation studies. The data analysis technique employed quantitative data processed with SPSS version 24, including t- tests, the coefficient of determination (R²), and the Sobel test. The results of this study indicate that there is a significant influence between the variables of employee engagement, organizational justice, and job satisfaction on performance. The job satisfaction variable can influence the employee engagement and organizational justice variables on performance. The ability of the employee engagement, organizational justice, and job satisfaction variables to explain employee performance at PT. Berkat Bima Sentana is 84.2%, while the remaining 15.8% is explained by other variables not included in this research model.

Keywords : *Employee Engagement, Organizational Justice, Job Satisfaction, Performance*

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Introduction

In the Industrial Era 4.0, where business competition is increasingly fierce due to the rapid development of technology and information, investment in development, training and management of human resources is the key to achieving competitive advantage and sustainable growth. The performance of human resources is very important because they bring the knowledge, skills and creativity needed to face challenges, encourage innovation and improve overall organizational performance. As planners, implementers and controllers, company employees play an important role in achieving organizational goals, with their performance reflected in maximum effort in completing tasks, measured based on predetermined standards, targets, objectives or criteria. Effective employee management is the key to achieving optimal company performance and achieving company goals.

Performance comes from job performance or actual performance, which means work performance or actual achievements achieved by someone. Performance is the result of work that can be observed and measured. This can be seen from how many achievements are achieved, and the ability to complete the work at the company. Performance is the result of work or work performance in terms of quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out their functions in accordance with the responsibilities given to them (Khan et.al., 2010). The higher the achievement of targets and achievements, the more it will affect the value of a company. Employee performance plays an

important role in achieving company goals. Maximum better service can be achieved in a company in accordance with the authority and responsibility of each employee in realizing company goals. Performance is also the result of work produced or contributed by an employee related to duties and responsibilities to the company (Mangkunegara, 2010:13). Good employee performance helps companies become superior and successful in competition with other companies. Employee abilities will be reflected in their good performance and optimal performance. Performance refers to how well the job is done. When employees work well, the company can also achieve company goals effectively and efficiently

The factor that influences employee performance is job satisfaction. Job satisfaction reflects how good a person feels about his job, which is reflected in his positive attitude towards situations at work. Satisfied employees will give their best to the company and be loyal to the company. On the other hand, dissatisfaction can result in negative attitudes such as laziness, poor performance, or even leaving the company which has a negative impact on the company. In conclusion, job satisfaction is about how a person feels about their work, which is reflected in the way they handle their tasks. This is in line with research conducted by Rahmadani & Sampleiling (2023) showing that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Manihuruk (2023) shows that job satisfaction has a positive effect on employee performance. This means that when an employee feels job satisfaction, the employee will improve his performance.

The research gap with the results of research conducted by Kartika, et.al (2015) with the research title The Influence of Organizational Culture and Employee Engagement on Employee Performance at PT PLN (Persero) Bekasi Area shows that employee engagement has no significant effect on employee performance. In connection with the research gap mentioned above, the author uses the job satisfaction variable as an intervening or mediating variable in this research. This is in line with research conducted by Ramadan, et.al (2024) which shows employee engagement has no effect on employee performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Spirit at work

According to Khan et al. (2010), performance is work achievement (performance) both in terms of quantity and quality achieved by someone during a certain period, usually within one year. Noor (2013) believes "Employee performance is the result achieved by employees according to the standards applicable to the job in question."

Job satisfaction

According to Gibson (2000) job satisfaction is the attitude that workers have about their work. According to Kreitner and Kinicki (2001) job satisfaction is an affective or emotional response to various aspects of a person's work.

Employee Engagement

Employee engagement is the emotional commitment of employees to the organization and its goals. This emotional commitment means employees truly care about their work and the company. They do not work just for a salary, or just for a promotion, but work in the name of organizational goals. (Kruse, 2012). Employee engagement is the values implemented in a company which can be interpreted as the level of commitment and attachment that an employee has towards his company (Handoyo and Setiawan, 2017).

Organizational Justice

Organizational justice is about how employees feel they are treated fairly in the workplace. If employees feel that their organization is fair, they tend to be happier, more motivated, and committed to their work.

Conceptual framework

To make it easier to explain a study, the researcher describes a conceptual framework that contains the relationship between variables as follows

Figure 1. Research Model

A hypothesis is a temporary answer to a research problem, until proven through the data collected. The hypothesis of this research is:

1. H1 : Employee engagement influences employee job satisfaction PT. Berkat Bima Sentana.
2. H2 : Organizational justice influences employee job satisfaction at PT. Berkat Bima Sentana
3. H3 : Employee engagement influences employee performance at PT. Berkat Bima Sentana.
4. H4 : Organizational justice influences employee performance at PT. Berkat Bima Sentana.
5. H5 : Job satisfaction influences employee performance at PT. Berkat Bima Sentana
6. H6 : Employee engagement influences employee performance through job satisfaction at PT. Berkat Bima Sentana
7. H7 : Organizational justice influences employee performance through job satisfaction at PT. Berkat Bima Sentana.

2.1.5 Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistical analysis is analysis used to get an overview of the respondents in this research, especially to find out the respondents' general perceptions regarding the variables studied. This analysis was carried out using descriptive analysis to describe respondents' perceptions of the statement items submitted. Each respondent's answer was given an answer range between 1 and 5 according to the statement submitted. Descriptive statistical analysis was carried out on each research variable, namely organizational culture, work motivation, job satisfaction and employee performance. The descriptive statistical analysis provided is a description of the respondents' answers, namely employees of PT. Berkat Bima Sentana.

The interval class determination applied to all variables is:

1. The lowest value on the scale is 1 and the highest value on the scale is 5.
2. The class interval is $(5-1) / 5 = 0.80$

The class division can be seen in table 2.1.5 :

Table 2.1
Average Class Division of Respondents' Answers

Average Value Range	Class/Category
1,00 – 1,80	Very low /Very poor
1,81 – 2,60	Low/Not good
2,61 – 3,40	Medium/Neutral
3,41 – 4,20	High/Good
4,21 – 5,00	Very high/Very good

Source: Data processed from research results, 2024

2.1.6 Results of Descriptive Statistical Analysis of Employee Engagement Variables

Descriptive statistical analysis of respondents' answers regarding employee engagement variables is based on respondents' answers to statements as contained in the questionnaire distributed to respondents. Respondent answer variables can be seen in Table 2.2 below::

Table 2.2
Results of Descriptive Statistical Analysis of Employee Engagement Variables

Statement Items	Respondent's Answer							Standard Deviation	Average score	Category
	SS	S	RG	TS	STS	Total	f			
	%	%	%	%	%	%	%			
Q1	6	27	38	21	6	98		0,993	3,06	Medium
	6,1	27,6	38,8	21,4	6,1	100				
Q2	5	27	44	15	7	98		0,960	3,08	Medium
	5,1	27,6	44,9	15,3	7,1	100				
Q3	7	19	43	28	1	98		0,902	3,03	Medium
	7,1	19,4	43,9	28,6	1	100				
Q4	7	30	36	18	7	98		1,028	3,12	Medium
	7,1	30,6	36,7	18,4	7,1	100				
Q5	9	21	44	19	5	98		0,990	3,10	Medium
	9,2	21,4	44,9	19,4	5,1	100				
Q6	3	29	38	25	3	98		0,896	3,04	Medium
	3,1	29,6	38,8	25,5	3,1	100				
<i>Grand Mean Employee Engagement</i>									3,07	Medium

Source: Data processed from research results, 2024

Table 2.2 shows that on average the answers to each statement regarding employee engagement at PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana is in the medium category. Respondents' explanation of the statement "I am always enthusiastic about completing work.", where 6 people (6.1%) stated that they strongly agreed; 27 people (27.6%) agreed; 38 people (38.8%) stated they were undecided/neutral; 21 people (21.4%) said they disagreed; 6 people (6.1%) stated that they strongly disagree with an average value of 3.06, this shows that employees of PT. Thanks to Bima, Sentana has enough enthusiasm to complete his work.

Respondents' explanation of the statement "I don't get tired easily when working", where 5 people (5.1%) stated that they strongly agreed; 27 people (27.6%) agreed; 44 people (44.9%) stated they were undecided/neutral; 15 people (15.3%) said they disagreed; 7 people (7.1%) said they strongly disagreed, with an average value of 3.08, this shows that employees of PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana, you don't get tired easily when working.

Respondents' explanation of the statement "I have a commitment to carry out my duties as well as possible", where 7 people (7.1%) stated that they strongly agreed; 19 people (19.4%) agreed; 43 people (43.9%) stated they were undecided/neutral; 28 people (28.6%) said they disagreed; 1 person (1.0%) stated that they strongly disagreed, with an average value of 3.03, this shows that employees of PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana, he has sufficient commitment to carry out his duties as well as possible.

Respondents' explanation of the statement "I feel proud to be part of the company", where 7 people (7.1%) stated that they strongly agreed; 30 people (30.6%) agreed; 36 people (36.7%) stated they were undecided/neutral; 18 people (18.4%) said they disagreed; 7 people (7.1%) said they strongly disagreed, with an average value of 3.12, this shows that employees of PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana, he is quite proud to be part of the company.

Respondents' explanation of the statement "I feel time passes so quickly when working at the company.", where 9 people (9.2%) said they strongly agreed; 21 people (21.4%) agreed; 44 people (44.9%) stated they were unsure/neutral; 19 people (19.4%) said they disagreed; 5 people (5.1%) said they strongly disagreed, with an average value of 3.10, this shows that employees of PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana, he felt that time passed so quickly when he worked at the company.

Respondents' explanation of the statement "I feel my work is very interesting and challenging", where 3 people (3.1%) stated that they strongly agreed; 29 people (29.68%) agreed; 38 people (38.8%) stated they were doubtful/neutral; 25 people (25.5%) said they disagreed; 3 people (3.1%) said they strongly disagreed, with an average value of 3.04, this shows that employees of PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana, they find their work quite interesting and challenging.

Results of Descriptive Statistical Analysis of Organizational Justice Variables

Descriptive statistical analysis of respondents' answers regarding work motivation variables is based on respondents' answers to statements as contained in the questionnaire distributed to respondents. Respondent answer variables can be seen in Table 4.7 below.

Table 2.3
Results of Descriptive Statistical Analysis of Organizational Justice Variables

Statement Items	Respondent's Answer						Standard Deviation	Average score	Category
	SS	S	RG	TS	STS	Total			
	f	f	f	f	f	f			
	%	%	%	%	%	%			
Q1	4	35	45	13	1	98	0,786	3,29	Medium
	4,1	35,7	45,9	13,3	1,0	100			
Q2	6	33	36	22	1	98	0,900	3,21	Medium
	6,1	33,7	36,7	22,4	1,0	100			
Q3	4	29	43	21	1	98	0,837	3,14	Medium
	4,1	29,6	43,9	21,4	1,0	100			
Q4	4	40	40	11	3	98	0,845	3,32	Medium
	4,1	40,8	40,8	11,2	3,1	100			

Q5	8	38	35	17	0	98	0,868	3,38	Medium
	8,2	38,8	35,7	17,3	0	100			
Q6	12	32	40	11	3	98	0,950	3,40	Medium
	12,2	32,7	40,8	11,2	3,1	100			
<i>Grand Mean</i>								3,29	Medium

Source: Data processed from research results, 2024

Table 2.3 shows that on average the answers to each statement regarding PT organizational justice. Thanks to Bima Sentana is in the medium category. The respondent's explanation "the rewards I receive are commensurate with my workload.", where 4 people (4.1%) strongly agreed; 35 people (35.7%) agreed; 45 people (45.9%) stated they were undecided/neutral; 13 people (13.3%) said they disagreed; 1 person (1.0%) stated that they strongly disagreed, with an average value of 3.29, which is in the medium category, this shows that employees of PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana, he feels that the rewards he receives are quite commensurate with the workload.

The respondent's explanation of the statement "decisions regarding salary increases in companies are fair and transparent", where 6 people (6.1%) stated that they strongly agreed; 33 people (33.7%) agreed; 36 people (36.7%) stated they were unsure/neutral; 22 people (22.4%) said they disagreed; 1 person (1.0%) stated that they strongly disagreed, with an average value of 3.21, this shows that employees of PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana, he assessed that the decision regarding salary increases in the company was quite fair and transparent.

The respondent's explanation was the statement "I feel that the procedures used in decision making in the company are transparent.", where 4 people (4.1%) stated that they strongly agreed; 29 people (29.6%) agreed; 43 people (43.9%) stated they were undecided/neutral; 21 people (21.4%) said they disagreed; 1 person (1.0%) stated that they strongly disagreed, with an average value of 3.14, this shows that employees of PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana, he feels that the procedures used in decision making in the company are quite transparent.

Respondents' explanation of the statement "I am involved in the decision-making process related to my work.", where 4 people (4.1%) stated that they strongly agreed; 40 people (40.8%) agreed; 40 people (40.8%) stated they were undecided/neutral; 11 people (11.2%) said they disagreed, 3 people (3.1%) said they strongly disagreed, with an average value of 3.32, this shows that employees of PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana, they feel quite involved in the decision-making process related to their work.

The respondent's explanation of the statement "my superior treats me with respect and dignity", where 8 people (8.2%) stated that they strongly agreed; 38 people (38.8%) agreed; 35 people (35.7%) stated they were undecided/neutral, 17 people (17.3%) said they disagreed, with an average value of 3.38, this shows that employees of PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana, he feels that his superiors treat them with sufficient respect and dignity.

The respondent's explanation of the statement "I feel appreciated and respected by my colleagues.", where 12 people (12.2%) stated that they strongly agreed; 32 people (32.7%) agreed; 40 people (40.8%) stated they were undecided/neutral; 11 people (11.2%) said they disagreed; 3 people (3.1%) said they strongly disagreed, with an average value of 3.40, this shows that employees of PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana, they feel quite appreciated and respected by their colleagues.

2.1.7 Results of Descriptive Statistical Analysis of Job Satisfaction Variables

Descriptive statistical analysis of respondents' answers regarding job satisfaction variables is based on respondents' answers to statements as contained in the questionnaire distributed to respondents. Respondent answer variables can be seen in Table 2.4 below:

Table 2.4
Results of Descriptive Statistical Analysis of Job Satisfaction Variables

Statement Items	Respondent's Answer								
	SS	S	RG	TS	STS	Total	Standard Deviation	Average score	Category
	f	f	f	f	f	f			
	%	%	%	%	%	%			
Q1	11	25	40	18	4	98	1,008	3,21	Medium
	11,2	25,5	40,8	18,4	4,1	100			
Q2	8	22	40	26	2	98	0,949	3,08	Medium
	8,2	22,4	40,8	26,5	2,0	100			
Q3	12	23	40	18	5	98	1,042	3,19	Medium
	12,2	23,5	40,8	18,4	5,1	100			
Q4	8	26	39	22	3	98	0,963	3,14	Medium
	8,2	26,5	39,8	22,4	3,1	100			
Q5	9	26	36	24	3	98	0,995	3,14	Medium
	9,2	26,5	36,7	24,5	3,1	100			
Q6	8	27	36	23	4	98	0,998	3,12	Medium
	8,2	27,6	36,7	23,5	4,1	100			

Source: Data processed from research results, 2024

Table 4.8 shows that on average the answers to each statement regarding job satisfaction at PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana is in the medium category. The respondent's explanation of the statement "I work according to my talents or abilities", where 11 people (11.2%) stated that they strongly agreed; 25 people (25.5%) agreed; 40 people (40.8%) said they were undecided/neutral, 18 people (18.4%) said they disagreed; 4 people (4.1%) stated that they strongly disagree with an average value of 3.21, this shows that employees of PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana, they work according to their gifts or talents.

The respondent's explanation of the statement "I love the job I am doing now", where 8 people (8.2%) stated that they strongly agreed; 22 people (22.4%) agreed; 40 people (40.8%) stated they were undecided/neutral; 26 people (26.5%) said they disagreed; 2 people (2.0%) said they strongly disagreed, with an average value of 3.08, this shows that employees of PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana, they really love the work they are doing now.

The respondent's explanation of the statement "I feel satisfied with the salary I receive from the company", where 12 people (12.2%) stated that they strongly agreed; 23 people (23.5%) agreed; 40 people (40.8%) stated they were undecided/neutral; 18 people (18.4%) said they disagreed; 5 people (5.1%) said they strongly disagreed, with an average value of 3.19, this shows that employees of PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana, they are quite satisfied with the salary they receive from the company.

The respondent's explanation of the statement "the company is fair in terms of giving salaries to employees", where 8 people (8.2%) stated that they strongly agreed; 26 people (26.5%) agreed; 39 people (39.8%) stated they were undecided/neutral; 22 people (22.4%) said they disagreed; 3 people (3.1%) said they strongly disagreed, with an average value of 3.14, this shows that employees of PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana, he believes that the company is quite fair in terms of giving salaries to employees.

The respondent's explanation of the statement "the company provides promotion opportunities to every employee in a transparent manner", where 9 people (9.2%) stated that they strongly agreed; 26 people (26.5%) agreed; 36 people (36.7%) said they were undecided/neutral, 24 people (24.5%) said they disagreed; 3 people (3.1%) said they strongly disagreed, with an average value of 3.14, this shows that employees of PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana, it is sufficient for the company to provide promotion opportunities to each employee in a transparent manner.

The respondent's explanation of the statement "colleagues support each other in order to achieve common goals", where 8 people (8.2%) stated that they strongly agreed; 27 people (27.6%) agreed; 36 people (36.7%) said they were doubtful/neutral, 23 people (23.5%) said they disagreed; 4 people (4.1%) said they strongly disagreed, with an average value of 3.12, this shows that employees of PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana, they feel that their colleagues are quite supportive of each other in order to achieve common goals.

The respondent's explanation of the statement "supervisors supervise employees well", where 7 people (7.1%) stated that they strongly agreed; 30 people (30.6%) agreed; 37 people (37.8%) stated they were undecided/neutral; 17 people (17.3%) said they disagreed; 7 people (7.1%) stated that they strongly disagreed, with an average value of 3.13, this shows that employees of PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana, they feel that their superiors supervise their employees quite well.

2.1.8 Results of Descriptive Statistical Analysis of Employee Performance Variables

Descriptive statistical analysis of respondents' answers regarding employee performance variables is based on respondents' answers to statements as contained in the questionnaire distributed to respondents. Respondent answer variables can be seen in Table below:

Table 2.5
Results of Descriptive Statistical Analysis of Employee Performance Variables

Statement Items	Respondent's Answer						Standard Deviation	Average score	Category
	SS	S	RG	TS	STS	Total			
	f	f	f	f	f	f			
	%	%	%	%	%	%			
Q1	11	39	26	19	3	98	1,019	3,37	Medium
	11,2	39,8	26,5	19,4	3,2	100			
Q2	10	29	41	18	0	98	0,892	3,32	Medium
	10,2	29,6	41,8	18,4	0	100			
Q3	13	34	44	5	2	98	0,864	3,52	Good
	13,3	34,7	44,9	5,1	2,0	100			
Q4	15	24	37	18	4	98	1,065	3,29	Medium
	15,3	24,5	37,8	18,4	4,1	100			
Q5	12	37	34	11	4	98	0,984	3,43	Good
	12,2	37,8	34,7	11,2	4,1	100			
Q6	12	33	41	10	2	98	0,909	3,44	Good
	12,2	33,7	41,8	10,2	2,0	100			
<i>Grand Mean</i>								3,40	Medium

Source: Data processed from research results, 2024

Table 2.5 shows that on average the answers to each statement regarding employee performance at PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana is in the medium category.

The respondent's explanation was the statement "the results of my work are in accordance with the standards determined by the company", where 11 people (11.2%) stated that they strongly agreed; 39 people (39.8%) agreed; 26 people (26.5%) stated they were undecided/neutral; 19 people (19.4%) said they disagreed; 3 people (3.1%) said they strongly disagreed, with an average value of 3.37, this shows that some employees of PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana that the results of their work are quite in accordance with the standards set by the company.

The respondent's explanation of the statement "my supervisor is satisfied with the quality of my work", where 10 people (10.2%) stated that they strongly agreed; 29 people (29.6%) agreed; 41 people (41.8%) stated they were undecided/neutral; 18 people (18.4%) said they disagreed, with an average value of 3.32, this shows that employees of PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana, he feels that his superiors are quite satisfied with the results of their work.

The respondent's explanation of the statement "I work according to a predetermined schedule", where 13 people (13.3%) stated that they strongly agreed; 34 people (34.7%) agreed; 44 people (44.9%) stated they were undecided/neutral; 5 people (5.1%) said they disagreed; 2 people (2.0%) stated that they strongly disagreed, with an average value of 3.52, this shows that employees of PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana for working according to the predetermined schedule.

The respondent's explanation of the statement "I have enough time to complete the work", where 15 people (15.3%) stated that they strongly agreed; 24 people (24.5%) agreed; 37 people (37.8%) stated they were undecided/neutral; 18 people (18.4%) said they disagreed; 4 people (4.1%) said they strongly disagreed, with an average value of 3.29, this shows that employees of PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana sufficient time to complete their work.

The respondent's explanation of the statement "I have the ability to collaborate with other people", where 12 people (12.2%) stated that they strongly agreed; 37 people (37.8%) agreed; 34 people (34.7%) stated they were undecided/neutral; 11 people (11.2%) said they disagreed; 4 people (4.1%) said they strongly disagreed, with an average value of 3.43, this shows that employees of PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana, he has the ability to work well with other people.

The respondent's explanation of the statement "I do not experience obstacles in collaborating with colleagues", where 12 people (12.2%) stated that they strongly agreed; 33 people (33.7%) agreed; 41 people (41.8%) stated they were unsure/neutral; 10 people (10.2%) said they disagreed; 2 people (2.0%) said they strongly disagreed, with an average value of 3.44, this shows that employees of PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana, there are no obstacles in collaborating with colleagues.

CONCLUSION

1. Employee engagement has a significant effect on employee job satisfaction at PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana.
2. Organizational Justice has a significant effect on PT employee job satisfaction. Thanks to Bima Sentana.
3. Employee engagement has a significant effect on employee performance at PT. Thanks to Bima Sentana
4. Organizational Justice has a significant effect on the performance of PT employees. Thanks to Bima Sentana.
5. Job satisfaction has a significant effect on the performance of PT employees. Thanks to Bima Sentana..
6. Employee engagement has a significant effect on the performance of PT employees. Thanks to Bima Sentana through job satisfaction.
7. Organizational justice has a significant effect on the performance of PT employees. Thanks to Bima Sentana through job satisfaction.

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